

Managing Diversity: An English Coordinator's Experiences among its Stakeholders

Keth Arcilla Villanueva

Abstract:- This study's primary purpose was to identify how an English school coordinator works with its stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, students, and principals. The study used a descriptive and qualitative research design to identify the diversity management of English school coordinators toward stakeholders. The qualitative process used thematic analysis of the participant's experiences managing diversity among stakeholders. The results revealed that understanding the teacher's personal and professional qualities is vital for English school coordinators to manage diversity better. Further, being an English school coordinator in managing diversity requires relationships with parents to allow the latter to be motivated and cooperative in knowing the progress and development of their children in the school. Additionally, English school coordinators are responsible for the needs of the students in the school and the subject, thereby pushing teachers and school leaders to manage lessons for the diverse students through student-centered approaches. Lastly, as school coordinators, managing diversity does not revolve only around the students, teachers, and parents but also towards school leaders or principals. This study concludes that managing diversity among stakeholders is vital to the school's progress. Collaboration with stakeholders can uplift an organization in times of uncertainty and challenges. This study recommends all English school coordinators strengthen their relationships with the stakeholders, equate their feelings and emotions properly, propel their engagement in the different workshops about diversity management, and encourage subordinates to attend sessions about student-centered teaching strategies. It is further recommended for schools to use technology to better trace stakeholders' information.

Keywords:- Diversity management, stakeholders & English school coordinator

I. INTRODUCTION

The school has been the second home of every student, teacher, and other stakeholders. For every school, stakeholders are the ones who also give life and nurture other stakeholders regardless of their background. The school offers enriched and substantive lessons and inclusivity for every stakeholder within and outside the school. Stakeholders can be uplifted and recognized through the efforts done by a leader or a manager. The school or a company can be productive and proactive in addressing the problems in the future once the manager and or a leader exemplifies a deep appreciation of the stakeholders' diverse backgrounds. With

the pressing demands in today's new educational landscape, a leader may forget diversity management that allows stakeholders to unite to work and operate as one.

School leaders like English school coordinators work with their subordinates to help one another in tackling issues about the school, students, parents, co-teachers, or even other stakeholders. The English school coordinator operates by equally dividing subordinates with designated work on what to comply with and what to do when problems arise. The English school coordinators are the ones who will be exemplary in managing diversity among every stakeholder. In today's new educational landscape, the different school coordinators experienced problems addressing diversity management amid the pandemic. Since school is the second home in which parents and students can rely and put much trust, the school should maintain equal diversity management to engage students to learn to bring parents together and encourage teachers, the principal, and other stakeholders to work together.

Diversity management encompasses the differences people bring to an organization or group (Redondo,2006). Diversity in school teaches all stakeholders how to live and work in a society. Connecting with peers, co-workers, parents, and students with diverse backgrounds and abilities is valuable as it develops a rapport relationship with one another. The influential role of teachers enhances quality education and creates a healthy learning environment in school (Chen & Velsor, 1996). Thus, English school coordinators should also manage diversity towards other teachers, for they are the ones who cascade diversity management towards the parents, students, and as well as other stakeholders.

It is quite a challenge for every English school coordinator to address stakeholders' needs and interests from diverse backgrounds. The school contains employees or stakeholders with various demographic and socio-cultural characteristics that the school leader or coordinators should recognize and appreciate. But, it needs to be addressed and managed well for the all-around development of the learners and other stakeholders (Lewis, 2000). Diversity management controls diversities from a managerial perspective and deals with the management style of organizations and administrators (Surveil et al.,2008). Furthermore, Hopkins and Hopkins (1999) stated that diversity is not a problem but can be managed.

English school coordinators play a vital role in the school in which they manage the problems of the students towards learning the complexity of the language, they tend to address the gaps between English teachers towards the students in the language instruction, and they manage to intervene and converse with the parents about the development and progress of their children. However, when the COVID-19 pandemic abruptly changed the educational system, the English school coordinators forgot how to divide the subordinates to cater to the needs of the students, parents, the principal, and other stakeholders. On the other hand, other English school coordinators equally divide the subordinates to cater to the needs of the stakeholders. However, it has been a problem for English school coordinators in addressing the needs of the students and how to communicate co-English teachers or subordinates to maintain the performance level of their department. In addition, English school coordinators have difficulty engaging the parents to be participative and cooperative towards the development of their children and how to be responsible and proactive in the demands of the principal amidst diverse backgrounds and socio-cultural characteristics. When differences are handled, stakeholders' differences may help the emergence of creative ideas in the direction of different perspectives and opinions. As a result, this may help the productivity of the school. Hence, when individual and socio-cultural differences are managed and conducted correctly, it would produce a productive effect in achieving the school's goals. Showers (2016) stated that the differences among employees perform 35% better than in similar but more homogeneous organizations. However, divisions, conflicts, and commitment may decrease when differences are not appropriately managed. Consequently, English school coordinators, as one of the school's stakeholders, should work diversity in the workplace as they are also crucial in promoting the school to its highest state. English school coordinators, as one the leaders of the department in the school, are put under pressure as to how they manage stakeholders' differences and how they can acquire new and beneficial ideas to them in continuing to give quality education amid the pandemic. Dotlich, Cairo, and Rhinesmith (2009) stated that, in some circumstances, leaders' abilities might be insufficient regardless of how empathic and effective they may be. In addition, it is necessary to utilize and benefit stakeholders' ideas in developing new strategies for understanding and analyzing problems. Thus, it helps the diversity of abilities to create positive impacts on the effectiveness of actions and shows that the diversity of the group is way better than the mastery when finding solutions (Liam, 2015). Thus, diversity in the workplace is a significant element of an organization. The diversity management of English school coordinators revolves around the four stakeholders: parents, teachers, students, and the principal. This study's results provide valuable input to the English school coordinators in managing diversity among stakeholders

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study's objective was to point out the diversity management practices of an English school coordinator toward other stakeholders.

Specifically, it intended to:

1. Identify the ways of an English school coordinator toward other stakeholders;
 - Teachers
 - Parents
 - Students
 - Principal and;
2. Propose a recommendation for managing diversity during this pandemic.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive research design. It utilized a qualitative research method to describe the diversity management of English school coordinator toward stakeholders. The qualitative process used thematic analysis of the participant's experiences managing diversity among stakeholders. The questionnaire was researcher-made. The statements were based on the participant's experiences in managing diversity. The study participant was an English school coordinator from one of the public schools in the Northern part of Cebu, specifically in Kawit, Medellin Cebu. A coding was adopted and used to analyze the qualitative data obtained from the interview questions. To further explain the data, the English school coordinator was given four categories that consisted of five questions. The four categories are mainly known as stakeholders in the school. The four stakeholders are teachers, parents, students, and the principal. The questions revolved around the diversity management of the English school coordinator in responding to the diversity of the given four stakeholders. The responses given were transcribed to substantiate the data, and coding followed afterward. According to (Gibbs, 2007), coding is a process of identifying a passage in the text or other data, searching and identifying concepts, and finding relations between them. Thus, coding is a way of indexing or categorizing the text to establish a framework of thematic ideas about it. Afterward, themes were generated based on the participant's significant statements, and core categories were identified after verifying the comparison articles.

Ethical considerations were observed and realized in the study. The identity of the locale and respondent were protected with high confidentiality and deemed under privacy. The school principal was given a transmittal letter through email and the English school coordinator to permit their approval and time to participate in the study. The participant was given the interview questions through email and invited through Google Meet to discuss their experiences in managing diversity since only the participant was allowed to join the Google Meet set by the researcher. When the core categories and recommendations were generated, it was then brought to the participant and the school as a basis for proof and as means of reflection in recognizing the importance of diversity among stakeholders.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the study's results based on the participant's responses and experiences in managing diversity. The following are the core categories based on the themes analyzed from the given responses of the participant.

Core Categories of the Responses of English School Coordinator in Managing Diversity towards Stakeholders

The participant shared her ways of managing diversity among stakeholders. The significant statements were extracted from the raw data. Themes and core categories were identified as shown in Table 1.

THEMES	CORE CATEGORIES
Empathy to colleagues	Understanding teachers' personal and professional qualities
Professionalism, documentation of events/ following of proper channels	
Ways to maintain a positive outlook	
Understanding towards positive and better communication	
Collaborative way in decision making	Parent-teacher engagement
Parent-teacher relationship for the better learning experience	
Involvement of parents in the learning process	
Involvement of parents in the class standing/ level of assessment of their child's progress	
Responding to parent's queries/ feedback/ emotions	Student-centered approach in the classroom
Management	
Goal creation/ rules and regulations for the class	
Real-life applications of topics, strategies, promoting real-life scenarios to the students	
Anecdotal records processes in decorum	
Equality in the classroom	
Democratic handling of students	
Coping mechanisms in stress	
Responsibilities of a teacher	
Characteristics of a leader	
Professionalism and responses in accepting criticisms	Teachers' and school coordinators responsibilities
Role model	

Table 1:- Coding Process to Identify the Core Categories

There were 21 themes extracted from the raw responses of the English school coordinator, and core categories were identified to give a conceptual meaning to the themes. There were four core categories generated from the 21 themes.

Understanding Teacher's Personal and Professional Qualities was a core category generated from the 21 themes. The English school coordinator is one of the leaders in the school that upholds the leadership towards other teachers in responding to the needs of the students and the school. Understanding the different qualities of the teachers is vital and a must as an English school coordinator. Influential diversity leaders should recognize themselves first. Their followers next, be sensitive and aware of cultural and social differences, uphold awareness of this issue, support diversity to avoid static organizational structure, and support the emergence of new diverse leaders in the organization (Aguirre & Martinez, 2006 as cited by Polat, 2017). Hopkins and Hopkins (1999), as cited by Arslan (2017), listed the characteristics of influential diversity leaders as care, objectivity, mediation, tolerance, sincerity, instructiveness diversity of individuals regardless of the differences, and political view by making use of such diversity of individuals and directing people with common objectives by holding them together in harmony (Polat & Olcum, 2016, p. 72).

Being an English school coordinator in managing diversity among the parents requires relationships that allow parents to be motivated and cooperative in knowing the

progress and development of their children in the school. An English school coordinator needs to understand the importance of managing diversity towards the parents since parents are one of the stakeholders in the school regardless of their diverse backgrounds. Consequently, English school coordinators should value the diversity of the parents because they can also help the students' progress. As the English school coordinator mentioned, *"Motivate parents to support the homework of the students and make sure parents feel listened to and involve parents in every school activity. Inform parents of their child's achievements, give comments on their child's progress, conduct home visitation for slow learners, and work together with the parents to find the solution."* The progress of the department or the school also lies with the parents as they are one of the stakeholders that help schools to be productive.

The core category of the *student-centered approach in the classroom* is described in the themes of the participant. English school coordinators are responsible for the needs of the students in the school and the subject. With the students' diverse backgrounds, teachers or school leaders are pressured to manage the lessons for the diverse students in the four-cornered classroom. Teaching diversity in the classroom is a vital part of establishing and forming an overall school policy of cultural diversity. The schools can play a vital part to promote policies and procedures for equality, diversity, and inclusion in schools. Still, teachers can implement diversity and inclusiveness in the classroom daily with their students.

It is vital to provide our students the safest educational environments and experiences and include teaching diversity in the classroom. It requires not only creating physically safe and secure spaces but also protecting and promoting students' emotional health, making them feel validated, nurtured, and included. As school leaders, teachers, and managers, it is significant to practice equality and diversity in teaching and promote inclusion among students. The school can strive to create culturally diverse safe spaces that encourage, welcome, and celebrate students' differences. As prescribed by Republic Act No. 10533, DepEd shall adhere that the curriculum shall be learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally relevant, and appropriate, and the curriculum shall be culture-sensitive, which means that instruction must respect the cultural identities of the learners. Thus, it is vital for the English school coordinators in the school to inform the subordinates of the strategies and methods of teaching that cater to the diverse learners from diverse backgrounds. As the English school coordinator mentioned, "*Show fair treatment to all the students and promote positive behaviors, be a democratic style, meaning let students say something that they would like, make an anecdotal recording and reach out to subordinates for support and by connecting what you are teaching to real-life situations.*"

Lastly, *teachers' & school coordinators' responsibilities* as one of the four categories derived from the 21 themes in managing diversity. As school coordinators, it does not mean that managing diversity revolves only around the students, teachers, and parents but also towards school leaders or principals. Managing diversity brings school coordinators to know and value their responsibilities given by the school principals or school leaders regardless of who they are and where they are from. Understanding coordinators' responsibilities also require developing a healthy relationship with the principal. Leaders are pivotal in carrying out diversity-related initiatives. However, the leadership challenge in addressing diversity issues is often complicated by the leaders' exposure to others different from themselves and their ability to address racial concerns (Thomas, 2008, as cited by Young et al., 2010). School administrators must create an inclusive culture that requires them to be adaptable, flexible, and value diversity (Madsen & Mabokela, 2005; Thomas, 2008, as cited by Young et al., 2010). The school's progress lies in the stakeholders and how each subordinate functions in their role effectively. Managing diversity is as essential as giving quality education to students. An effective leader encourages and promotes equity and equality in the organization (Lim, 2015). Equity does not refer to basing preferences for someone over others upon biases and stereotypes. Biases may cause unfair evaluations and favoritism. Followers' justice perceptions and trust towards leaders decrease (Glanz, 2002). If diversities are wished to be used for organizational benefit, leaders should have an objective attitude and not have any prejudices toward followers. Employees feel negative when they feel they are not treated fairly (Hopkins and Hopkins, 1999). Diversity leadership aims to change beliefs, policies, and practices that shape the organization towards the inclusion of diversities and building objectivity (Owen, 2009). Some of the

competencies of administrators are needed to achieve equity in an organization are to create an organizational capacity that can meet the diverse and changing needs of society, can lead the changes that will decrease inequality, can act in the context of human rights, and can provide effective equality in the improvement and planning activities of the school (Ali, Burns & Grant, 2013).

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that managing diversity among stakeholders is vital and salient in the school's progress. Therefore, English school coordinators should continue to uphold diversity management towards other stakeholders for it gives solutions or interventions to the pressing problems in the school. The students, parents, teachers, principals, and other stakeholders are the people who bring the organization to its highest state. Management diversity is one of the essential requirements in making the school's progress soar high as it continues to cultivate excellence. These stakeholders are significant in helping teachers, school administrators, school coordinators, and school principals mold students to become competent. Thus, it is the responsibility of the school organization to cascade the information about the importance of diversity management to the teachers, coordinators, and administrators to learn more about diversity management and its impacts on the students' learning. By collaborating with the stakeholders, an organization can be uplifted in times of uncertainty and challenges. For all English school coordinators, it is recommended that they need to strengthen more of their relationships, equate their feelings and emotions properly, propel their engagement in the different workshops about diversity management, and encourage and provide subordinates to attend more sessions about student-centered strategies in teaching to inspire students to learn regardless of their diverse backgrounds and need to accept their responsibilities as English school coordinators irrespective of who the leaders or principal are. Lastly, it is recommended that the school should touch more on the technological field to better trace the stakeholders' information and can access them easily towards them.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Aguirre, A. & Martinez, R. O. (Eds.) (2006). Diversity leadership in higher education. ASHE Higher Education Report, 32(3), 1-113. <http://au.wiley.com/WileyCDA/WileyTitle/productCd-0787995789.html>
- [2]. Ali, S., Burns, C. & Grant, L. (2013). Equality and diversity in the health service. *Journal of Psychological Issues in Organizational Culture*, 3(S1), 190-209. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jpoc.21092>
- [3]. Anderson, L. (2014). Leadership, diversity, and inclusion. In T. S. O'Connell, B. Cuthbertson & T. J. Goins, (Eds.), *Leadership in recreation and leisure services*, (pp. 68-95). Human Kinetics.
- [4]. Brown, T. A. (2006). *Confirmatory factor analysis for applied research*. New York: Guilford Publications, Inc.

- [5]. Buyukozturk, S. (2007). Data analysis manual for social sciences. Ankara: Pegem A Publications. Capowski, G. (1996). Managing diversity. *Management Review*, 85(6), 12-19. <https://www.questia.com/magazine/1G1-18358662/managing-diversity>
- [6]. Chin, J. L., Desormeaux, L. & Sawyer, K. (2016). Making way for paradigms of diversity leadership. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 68(1), 49-71. <http://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/cpb0000051>
- [7]. Dotlich, D. L., Cairo, P. C. & Rhinesmith, S. H. (2009). *Leading in times of crisis: Navigating through complexity, diversity, and uncertainty to save your business.* Wiley. <http://au.wiley.com/WileyCDA/WileyTitle/productCd-047040230X.html>
- [8]. Doyle, R. & George, U. (2008). Achieving and measuring diversity: An organizational change approach. *Social Work Education*, 27(1), 97-110. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02615470601141235>